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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MUNDARIJA

Alohida ehtiyojga muhtoj bolalarga matematika darslarida integratsion yondashuvni amalga oshirish	10
Mamadjanova Ma'muraxon Kadirjanovna	
O'quvchilarda raqamli madaniyatni shakllantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	13
Boltayeva Go'zal Komilovna	
Inkluziv ta'lim sharoitida o'qituvchilarning metodik tayyorgarligini aniqlash metodologiyasi	21
D. Sh. Jo'rayeva, J. A. Jovliyev	
Bolalarda leksik-grammatik nutq kamchiliklarini bartaraf etishda kontekstli texnologiyalardan foydalanish	25
Abdullayeva Yoqutjon Qalandar qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining kognitiv qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish metodikasi	30
Abduvaliyeva Sabina Kurbonali qizi	
O'g'il bolalarni oilaviy munosabatlarga tayyorlashning pedagogik-psixologik asoslari.....	35
Aripov Shokirjon Olimovich, Raxmatillayeva Sug'diyona Muhammadjon qizi	
Pedagogik intuitsiyani rivojlantirishga yo'naltirilgan zamonaviy metodikalar	39
Axmedov Jaloliddin Oribovich	
The Impact of AI-Generated English Learning Materials Based on Uzbek Rural Life on the Learning Motivation of Rural Students.....	42
Baxramova Malika Muzaffarovna	
Raqamli kutubxonalarda sun'iy intellekt imkoniyatlaridan foydalanish texnologiyalari va imkoniyatlari	47
Choriyeva Zarina Anvarbek qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida orfografik savodxonlikni shakllantirishning nazariy-pedagogik asoslari ...	50
D. Teshaboyev, M. Sotvoldiyeva	
Oliy ta'limda tblt metodik modeli asosida baholash tizimini takomillashtirish	53
Djurayeva Nargiza Kudratillayevna	
Yangi O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida pedagogik etikaning rivojida xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	59
Dushayeva Nazokat Sharofiddinovna	
Uilyam Shekspir tragediyalarining o'zbek adabiyotidagi o'rni.....	62
Ergasheva Mehriyona	
Qizlarning oilaviy kompetensiyasi uchun ijodiy pedagogika: Koreya dizayn ta'limi modelini O'zbekiston kontekstiga moslash.....	65
G'ayratova Mohidil Zafar qizi	
Jismoniy tarbiya darslarida va darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarda umumrivojlantiruvchi mashqlardan foydalanish metodikasi	69
Maksetova Nurjamal Kuatovna	
Integrativ ta'lim muhitida bo'lajak surdopedagoglarning metodik kompetensiyalarini shakllantirish	72
Malikova Xurshida Ikramovna	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarda ko'p uchraydigan tovush talaffuzi kamchiliklari va ularni bartaraf etishda lopedik usullar.....	75
Moxirabonu G'aniyeva Adxam qizi	
Talabalarga an'anaviy xonandalik ijrochiligini o'rgatishning pedagogik yondashuvlari.....	78
Muxammadova Ozoda Muzrabovna	
Hayotiy sifat tushunchasini psixologik mazmuni.....	82
N. G. Pulatova	
Inklyuziv ta'lim sharoitida alohida ehtiyojlarga ega o'quvchilarni qo'llab-quvvatlashning kompleks yondashuvlari	85
Nazarova Dildora Asatovna, Abdurashidova Feruza Qaxramonovna	
Inklyuziv ta'lim tizimida o'qituvchining ko'p qirrali pedagogik faoliyati va uning nazariy asoslari	89
Nazarova Dildora Asatovna, Axmedova Aziza Temurovna	

Xo'ja ahmad Yassaviy e'tiqod tarbiyasi haqida.....	93
<i>Norova Sevara Uyg'un qizi</i>	
Matritsa va uning determinanti mavzusini o'qitish orqali bo'lajak iqtisodchilarning analitik tafakkurini rivojlantirish texnologiyalari.....	97
<i>Nuriddinov Jalolxon Tursunboy o'g'li, Otaboyev Muxsinjon Muqimjonovich</i>	
Odam anatomiyasi darslarida interfaol va multimedia vositalaridan foydalanish yo'llari.....	104
<i>Nurmatov Norqobil Jo'rayevich, Qo'chqorova Moxira Dilmurod qizi, Boxodirova Nilufar Ikrom qizi</i>	
AQSh ta'lim tizimining o'ziga xos jihatlari va bugungi kundagi rivojlanishi.....	110
<i>Orishev Jamshid Bahodirovich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf ona tili darslarida nutqiy kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishda xorijiy ta'limi tajribalari.....	116
<i>Pardayeva Gulbahor Jalg'ashovna</i>	
Kreativ ta'lim texnologiyalarining pedagogik mohiyati.....	119
<i>Sariboyev Nurali Abdunazarovich</i>	
Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'limning zamonaviy pedagogik tizimdagi o'rni.....	122
<i>Siddiqov Azamat Muhammadjon o'g'li</i>	
Konstruktiv yondashuv asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida 4K ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	126
<i>Sobirova Sarvinoz Quvondiqovna</i>	
Criteria of Scientific Activity Implementation of Physical Culture Education Students.....	133
<i>Sapayev Ruzmat Radjapovich</i>	
O'smir yoshdagi o'quvchilarning ma'naviy ehtiyojlarini shakllantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	136
<i>Tilovova Qizlarxon Ishpulat qizi</i>	
PIRLS tadqiqotida so'rovnomalarning qamrov doirasida maktab muhiti.....	141
<i>To'qliyeva Matluba Boqiyevna</i>	
Onlayn til o'rganish platformalarining esl o'quvchilarining og'zaki nutq ishonchi (speaking confidence) ga ta'siri.....	146
<i>Tojiboyeva Shohistaxon, Omonova Nargiza</i>	
Katta maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda dialogik nutqni rivojlantirishda kommunikativ o'yinlarning ahamiyati.....	151
<i>Toshpo'latova Sevinch O'ral qizi</i>	
Maktab o'quvchilarining jismoniy sifatlarini tarbiyalashning samarali uslublari.....	155
<i>Turdiyev Azam Xasanovich</i>	
O'quvchilarda tayanch kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirishda xalqaro baholash tizimini tatbiq etish imkoniyatlari.....	158
<i>Turobov Mamarajab Sodiq o'g'li</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda ijodiy va mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish.....	163
<i>Umirzoqova Surayyo Xudoyberdiyevna</i>	
Talabalarda perspektiv tasvir bajarishga oid ko'nikmani shakllantirishda CAD dasturlaridan amaliy foydalanish imkoniyatlari.....	165
<i>Valiyev A'zamjon Nematovich, Toxirov Sardorbek Muzaffar o'g'li</i>	
Duduqlanishni bartaraf etishda qo'llaniladigan usullar va vositalar.....	173
<i>Xasanova Barnoxon Abdusattor qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf ona tili darslarida o'quvchilarning yozma nutqini rivojlantirish usullari.....	176
<i>Xudoyberdiyeva Dildora Nazarjon qizi, Mambetova Lobar Mirzavali qizi</i>	
Duduqlanishga ega bolalar nutqini rivojlantirishda kompleks korreksion ishlar tizimi.....	179
<i>Xusanova Nozimaxon Zuxriddin qizi</i>	
Sirdaryo viloyatida tabiat va mehnat jarayonlarining tasviriy san'at orqali estetik va ekologik ifodasi.....	182
<i>Yorlaqova Malika Ahmad qizi</i>	
The Relevance of Artificial Intelligence in Teaching the English Language.....	186
<i>Yusupova Gulnoza Mirzoyevna</i>	
Umumta'lim maktabida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kuzatiladigan nutq xususiyatlari.....	189
<i>Zairova Nigora</i>	

Teatr texnologiyalarini maktabgacha ta'limga integratsiya qilishning pedagogik shartlari	193
<i>Abdullayeva Aziza Abdurazzoq qizi, Salimova Dilmira Farxodovna</i>	
Педагогические технологии совершенствования физических качеств как основы здорового образа жизни	197
<i>Журабаев Абдукарим Маматкулович</i>	
Формирование духовно-нравственной компетентности будущих учителей как педагогическая проблема	200
<i>Зокиржонova Ф. Р., Рихситиллаева Д. Р., Меликузиева Ш. А.</i>	
Межкультурный диалог как инструмент воспитания гармоничной личности в школе	203
<i>Махмудхожаев Ориф Бахтиёрвич</i>	
Talaba yoshlarining ma'naviy madaniyatini rivojlantirishda zamonaviy yondashuvlar	205
<i>Xojametov Ajiniyaz Andriyanovich</i>	
Методика формирования познавательных интересов у младших школьников в процессе выполнения творческих заданий на уроках русского языка	207
<i>Юлдашева Тахмина Бону Гайратовна</i>	
Raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalari asosida ingliz tili darslarida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini tinglab tushunishga o'rgatish usullari	210
<i>Abdurasulova Guljaxon Nabijon qizi</i>	
Fan va tabiatshunosligi asoslari mashg'ulotlarida tajribalar orqali bolalarning kognitiv qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish metodikasi	215
<i>Abdusamatova Nargiza Jamolidinovna, Xudayberganova Muqaddam Abdurashitovna</i>	
Bakteriofaglar tuzilishi va turlari (T-faglar) va ularning mikrobiekotizimdagi o'rni mavzusini o'qitish metodikasi	222
<i>Abdunazarova Zulayxo Sharifqulovna, Xo'janazarov O'ktam Eshtemirovich, Samikova Sevinch Toshtemir qizi</i>	
Bulung'ur doston ijrochiligining musiqiy xususiyatlari va ularni ta'lim jarayonida o'rgatishning pedagogik asoslari	227
<i>Babajanov Baxodir Allaberganovich</i>	
Activation of Students' Learning Activities Using Didactic Games	230
<i>Daminova Munajat Abduvoxobovna</i>	
Bolalar ensiklopediyasi vositasida tarbiyalanuvchilarning atrof-olam haqidagi tasavvurlarini shakllantirishning metodik shart-sharoitlari	234
<i>Davlatova Guljaxon Kamoliddin qizi</i>	
Innovatsion yondashuv asosida talabalarni kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlash metodikasini takomillashtirish	241
<i>Esanova Ro'shana Qurbonazarovna</i>	
Kreativ tafakkurning texnik muammolarni samarali hal qilishdagi o'rni va ahamiyati	248
<i>Imanov Baxtiyor Berdiyevich</i>	
Adabiyot va teatr san'ati vositasida maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ijobiy xulq-motivlarni shakllantirishda faollik markazlarining didaktik imkoniyatlari	253
<i>Inomova Dilnavoz Muzafar qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalari pedagog xodimlari mehnatini huquqiy tartibga solishning xususiyatlari	258
<i>Matekeyeva Bibinaz Mirjan qizi</i>	
Badiiy-estetik qadriyatlar va ularning o'ziga xosliklari	264
<i>Ostonova Gulrux Shuxrat qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilariga sharq allomalarining kitobxonlikka munosabatini tarixiy yondashuv asosida o'rgatishning ijtimoiy-tarixiy, zamonaviy va pedagogik xususiyatlari	268
<i>Parpiyayeva Zulayho Rahimjon qizi</i>	
Al-Xorazmiyning ilmiy merosi vositasida talabalarda analitik tafakkurni rivojlantirishning metodologik asoslari	272
<i>Qaxxorova Shaxnoza Abduvasit qizi</i>	
Musiqiy-badiiy did tarbiyasining ilmiy nazariy asoslari	276
<i>Rayimova Gavhar Karim qizi</i>	

Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ijtimoiy-muloqot kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda interfaol metodlardan foydalanish.....	279
<i>To'laboyeva Iqbolxon Olimjanovna</i>	
Malakaviy amaliyot orqali bo'lajak tarbiyachilarni kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantiruvchi texnologiyalari....	282
<i>Tohirjonova Hulkaroy Baxodir qizi</i>	
Bolalar musiqa va san'at maktabi o'quvchilariga chang cholg'usida Shashmaqom kuylarini o'rgatishning pedagogik yondashuvlari.....	288
<i>Toshpo'lotova Zulxumor Davlatboy qizi</i>	
Talabalarda axborot madaniyatini shakllantirishning xususiyatlari	292
<i>Usmonov Sh. F.</i>	
The Formation of Human Capital In Education: A Pedagogical and Economic Analysis	297
<i>Uzoqova Shohida Mirzamurod qizi</i>	
“Птицы во рту” Саманты Швоблин: каннибализм нежности и зооморфный код магического реализма	302
<i>Каримов Зиёахмад Алишер угли</i>	
Формирование профессиональных качеств будущих учителей через активизацию учебной деятельности студентов с использованием дидактических игр в педагогических вузах.....	307
<i>Расулова Исмигуль, Якубова Зухра</i>	
Bolalar adabiyotini rivojlantirishda innovatsion yondashuv	311
<i>Mirzayeva Nigora Bozorovna</i>	
Issues of Developing Communicative Competence in Future Teachers from the Point of View of an Andragogical Approach.....	314
<i>Nishanova Mastura Khafizovna</i>	
Raqamli va innovatsion ta'lim texnologiyalari vositasida bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida adabiy kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirish modeli.....	317
<i>Islomova Xafiza Azamatovna</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning testologik kompetentligini rivojlantirish muammosining ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	324
<i>Nuraliyev Islom Saidaliyevich</i>	
Концепт глаза в русской и узбекской лингвокультуре.....	328
<i>Кодирова Дилдора Абдуназар кизи, Асанов Руслан Арсенович</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ingliz tilida og'zaki nutq kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishda STEAM texnologiyasi asosida mashq tizimini takomillashtirish.....	334
<i>Eshonova Dilnoza Abrorovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich maktabda tabiiy fanlarni o'qitishning integratsiyalashgan dars shakllari va zamonaviy vositalari	337
<i>Bekmetova Shoxida Qodirberdiyevna, Nishonxo'jayeva E'zoza Nig'mon qizi</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'lim sharoitida bo'lajak tarbiya fani o'qituvchilarining deontologik kompetensiyasiga qo'yiladigan talablar.....	342
<i>Vaxobov Anvar Abdusattor o'g'li</i>	
Zoologiya darslarida “Qushlar sinfi” mavzusini o'qitishning didaktik tamoyillari va metodik imkoniyatlari....	347
<i>Xaqberdiyeva Shoiria Tursunaliyevna, Norboyeva Naima Begali qizi</i>	
O'quv tayyorlov guruhi gandbolchilarida mashg'ulot yuklamalarini rivojlantirish samaradorligi	352
<i>Shermuxamedova N.N., Saylavova Aida Alisher qizi</i>	
Ikkinchi tartibli differensial tenglamalar uchun lokal chegaraviy masalalar: nazariya va tatbiqlari.....	356
<i>Musurmanova Nilufar Allamurat qizi</i>	
“Boychechak” qo'shig'ida ajdodlar turmush tarzi motivlari.....	360
<i>S. Matchanov, U. F. Xabibullayev</i>	
Фразеологизмы русского языка как зеркало национальной картины мира: лингвокультурологи-ческий анализ и методика преподавания в современной школе	365
<i>Мустанов Убайдулло Зулпанович</i>	
Oliy ta'limda udl yondashuvi asosida inklyuziv ta'lim samaradorligini oshirish.....	369
<i>Yunusova Xusnora Shuxrat qizi</i>	

Art-pedagogik vositalar asosida talabalarning kasbiy mobilligini rivojlantirish.....	372
<i>Usmonova Qumriniso Saydaliyevna</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda didaktik o'yinlarning klassifikatsiyasi, pedagogik funksiyalari va raqamli ta'lim muhiti sharoitida integratsiyalashuvi.....	375
<i>Ortiqboeva Zumradxon Xasanboy qizi</i>	
Ta'lim jarayonida gamifikatsiya texnologiyasining qo'llanilishi.....	378
<i>Abdufatayev Sherjaxon Abduazimovich, Yaxshiboyev Temur-Malik Erkin o'g'li</i>	
Interaktiv o'yinlar asosida dasturlashni o'qitish: "Kod bo'lagini top" o'yinining pedagogik samaradorligi.....	381
<i>Xudayberganov Yashin Komilovich, Xonto'rayev Ibroxim Abdikamol o'g'li</i>	
Bo'lajak chet tili o'qituvchilarining kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	385
<i>Temirova Shoxsanam Komilovna</i>	
Kreativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishda akademik muhit va shaxslararo munosabatlarning psixologik mexanizmlari.....	389
<i>Abdurazzaqov Shuxratbek Zafarjon o'g'li</i>	
Talaba yoshlarda ma'naviy-axloqiy fazilatlarni shakllantirishning pedagogik mexanizmlari.....	392
<i>Fayziyeva Muqaddas Akbar qizi</i>	
STEAM ta'lim texnologiyasining mohiyati va uni boshlang'ich ta'limda qo'llash imkoniyatlari.....	397
<i>Abrorxonova Kamola Abrorxon qizi, Kamoljonova Iroda Niyazjon qizi</i>	
Zamonaviy yoshlar dunyoqarashining ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari.....	400
<i>Abdullayeva Nilufar Sadikjanovna</i>	
An'anaviy xonandalik ijrochiligida ovoz tarbiyasining shakl, usul va metodlari.....	403
<i>Abdusalomova Iroda Xabibulloyevna</i>	
Tibbiyot talabalari orasida kasbiy motivatsiyaning psixologik omillari.....	407
<i>Abduxamidov Abbas Muhiddin o'g'li, Rajabov Temurbek Baxtiyor o'g'li, Boboyeva Maxsuda Ataxanovna</i>	
Metakognitiv yondashuv asosida talabalar irodaviy sifatlarini rivojlantirishning kognitiv va psixologik asoslari.....	410
<i>Axatov Yo'ldoshjon Hamzayevich</i>	
A Model for Developing Transversal-Methodological Competencies in Future Educators.....	415
<i>Ergasheva Barno Ziyavitdin kizi</i>	
Historical Development of Project-Based Learning in Language Teaching.....	419
<i>Fayziyeva Ozoda Erkin Kizi</i>	
Axloq shakllanishining psixologik xususiyatlari: shaxs rivojlanishida ichki nazorat va motivatsiya mexanizmlari.....	423
<i>Ibaydayeva Munisa Aybek qizi</i>	
Neyropedagogik texnologiyalar asosida emotsional kompetentlikni rivojlantirishning innovatsion didaktik modeli.....	427
<i>Mirzaraxmonova Shaxnoza Mirzaaxmadovna</i>	
O'zbekistonda maktabgacha ta'limga xorijiy tajribalarni integratsiya qilish: Yaponiya davlati misolida.....	432
<i>Narimanova Saida Narimon qizi</i>	
Ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda yolg'on ma'lumotlar tarqalishining psixologik va ijtimoiy mexanizmlari hamda unga qarshi kurashish muammolari.....	436
<i>Nurmatov A. N.</i>	
Metodik savodxonlikni rivojlantirishning pedagogik va metodologik jihatlari (Biologiya fani misolida).....	439
<i>Rahimova Mahliyo Akramovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining yosh xususiyatlari va ularning matematik tafakkurini rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari.....	444
<i>Shabatova Rabig'a Janasbay qizi, Muxitdinova Nodira Mamalatifovna</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida talabalar ommaviy sportini rivojlantirishning pedagogik tizimini takomillashtirish konsepsiyasi.....	448
<i>Ummatov Nozim Raimjonovich</i>	
O'quv jarayonida differensial topshiriqlarning o'rni va ularning ahamiyati.....	453
<i>Xoldarova Irodaxon Valijonovna, Xakimova Ma'mura Davlatjon qizi</i>	

Biologiya ta'limida zamonaviy innovatsion texnologiyalarning o'rni	457
<i>Xaqberdiyeva Shoira Tursunaliyevna</i>	
Genetika mavzularini o'qitishda tahliliy faoliyatni tashkil etish metodlari, vositalari va shakllari.....	461
<i>Xaqberdiyeva Shoira Tursunaliyevna, Dosov Rustam Alisherovich</i>	
Hayvonlarning xilma- xilligi mazvusini o'qitishda multimedia, 3D format modellari va virtual lobaratoriya asosida o'qitish metodikasi	466
<i>Xaqberdiyeva Shoira Tursunaliyevna, Murodullayeva Sarvinoz O'tkirbek qizi</i>	
Tog'ayli baliqlar mavzusini o'qitishning didaktik tamoyillari, pedagogik shart-sharoitlari va metodik yondashuvlari.....	473
<i>Xaqberdiyeva Shoira Tursunaliyevna, Qodirova Nurshoda Olim qizi</i>	
A Comparative Analysis of Lexical Transformations in Abdulla Qahhor's Prose "Tolka"	478
<i>Kasimova Nafisa Farhodovna, Safarova Maftuna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari tarbiyasida ota-onalar bilan hamkorlikni tashkil etish metodikasi	482
<i>Fayziyeva Madinabonu Sohibjon qizi</i>	
Gnosiologik yondashuv asosida mustaqil ta'lim jarayonini loyihalash.....	485
<i>Xidirova Dildora Zayniddinovna</i>	
Nemis tilini o'qitishda sun'iy intellekt asosidagi ta'lim vositalari.....	491
<i>Xudoyberdiyeva Zumrat Xudayberdiyevna</i>	
Kasbiy nutqda til me'yorlariga rioya qilish muammolari.....	495
<i>Yuldasheva Dilnoza Bekmurodovna</i>	
Teatr texnologiyalarini maktabgacha ta'limga integratsiya qilishning pedagogik shartlari.....	498
<i>Abdullayeva Aziza Abdurazzoq qizi, Salimova Dilmira Farxodovna</i>	
Теоретические и практические аспекты развития одарённых студентов	502
<i>Байбаева Мухайё Худойбергеновна, Зайниддинова Хилола Абдулвахоб кизи</i>	
Организация проектной деятельности во внеурочной работе по математике при изучении темы "дроби" в начальных классах	508
<i>Бахытбаева Шахнозбану Махмуд кызы, Садыкова Альбина Венеровна</i>	
Традиционные методы развития навыка говорения в обучении иностранному языку	511
<i>Давронбекова Фарангис Давроновна</i>	
Описание скоростных качеств футболистов	517
<i>Мадаминов Орибджан Нишанбаевич</i>	

A MODEL FOR DEVELOPING TRANSVERSAL- METHODOLOGICAL COMPETENCIES IN FUTURE EDUCATORS

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Abstract: This annotation outlines the priority directions for modernizing the higher education system in Uzbekistan up to 2030. In this process, the development of independent learning, critical thinking, and transversal-methodical competencies in future preschool educators is defined as a key objective. The use of innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process serves to strengthen the professional training of future specialists. In particular, transversal-methodical competence integrates knowledge, creativity, and adaptability, enabling effective solutions to professional tasks. The study develops a model for training educators that includes goal-setting, systematic organization of educational content, and stages for competence assessment. This model creates a foundation for graduates to successfully operate in a modern educational environment.

Key words: higher education, Uzbekistan-2030, independent learning, critical thinking, pedagogical technologies, professional competence, transversal-methodical competence, competency-based approach.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu annotatsiyada O'zbekiston oliy ta'lim tizimini 2030-yilgacha modernizatsiya qilishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari yoritilgan. Mazkur jarayonda bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti tarbiyachilarida mustaqil ta'lim olish, tanqidiy fikrlash va transversal-metodik kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirish asosiy maqsad sifatida belgilangan. Ta'lim jarayonida innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish bo'lajak mutaxassislarining kasbiy tayyorgarligini mustahkamlashga xizmat qiladi. Xususan, transversal-metodik kompetensiya bilim, ijodkorlik va moslashuvchanlikni integratsiyalashgan holda kasbiy vazifalarni samarali hal etish imkonini beradi. Tadqiqotda maqsadni belgilash, ta'lim mazmunini tizimli tashkil etish va kompetensiyalarni baholash bosqichlarini o'z ichiga olgan pedagoglarni tayyorlash modeli ishlab chiqilgan. Ushbu model bitiruvchilarning zamonaviy ta'lim muhitida muvaffaqiyatli faoliyat yuritishi uchun zamin yaratadi.

Kalit so'zlar: oliy ta'lim, O'zbekiston-2030, mustaqil ta'lim, tanqidiy fikrlash, pedagogik texnologiyalar, kasbiy kompetensiya, transversal-metodik kompetensiya, kompetensiyaviy yondashuv.

Аннотация: В данной аннотации рассматриваются приоритетные направления модернизации системы высшего образования в Узбекистане до 2030 года. В данном процессе развитие самостоятельного обучения, критического мышления и трансверсально-методических компетенций у будущих педагогов дошкольного образования определяется как ключевая задача. Использование инновационных педагогических технологий в образовательном процессе способствует укреплению профессиональной подготовки будущих специалистов. В частности, трансверсально-методическая компетентность объединяет знания, креативность и адаптивность, обеспечивая эффективное решение профессиональных задач. В исследовании разработана модель подготовки педагогов, включающая целеполагание, системную организацию образовательного содержания и этапы оценки компетенций. Данная модель создает основу для успешной деятельности выпускников в современной образовательной среде.

Ключевые слова: высшее образование, Узбекистан-2030, самостоятельное обучение, критическое мышление, педагогические технологии, профессиональная компетентность, трансверсально-методическая компетентность, компетентностный подход.

INTRODUCTION

In the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, important tasks have been defined, including fostering students' independent learning, critical and creative thinking, and systematic thinking; developing entrepreneurial skills; introducing techniques and technologies aimed at competency development in the educational process; orienting the educational process toward the formation of practical skills; and extensively implementing advanced pedagogical technologies, training programs, and educational and methodological materials based on international educational standards. The

modernization of the educational system and the changes occurring in higher education are essential for the development of the professional competence of educational institution staff. Currently, state educational standards of higher education are being implemented, and innovations in educational content and technology are being widely introduced, aimed at improving the quality of training for future professional education teachers.

Transversal-methodological competence refers to integrated qualities based on an individual's general capacity to operate, as well as on the knowledge and experience manifested in their professional training. Thus, the concepts of competence and competency are broader than the concepts of knowledge, skills, and abilities, as they include such qualities as the integration of specialist knowledge into practical activities, foresight in identifying and solving problems, the ability to solve non-standard professional situations and complex tasks efficiently, productivity, flexibility in adapting to changing working conditions, and creative thinking skills. The development of the target component, which reflects a modern competitive professional personality, is associated with both internal and external factors. The state and society can be considered external factors, while personality traits represent internal factors. Through the interaction of these factors, a modern competitive personality is formed, enabling future educators to apply their professional skills not only in the training process but also in everyday life. The target component of the developed model, focused on the professional development of future educators based on a competency-based approach, determines the purpose of the activity, namely improving the technology of preparation for professional activity.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological component serves as the foundation for designing the process of developing the professional-pedagogical competence of future educators. The competency-based approach is applied in the educational process in accordance with the requirements of state educational standards (DTS) and qualifications. The development of professional-pedagogical competence is carried out through the use of pedagogical task-based methods, interactive educational technologies, didactic tools (such as tests, situational tasks, and creative exercises), and information and communication technologies.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The resultant component includes levels, indicators, and criteria of the professional competence of the future educator (excellent, good, average, acceptable), as well as the assessment of students' knowledge, skills, qualifications, activities, self-awareness, and control. Goal setting in the formation of professional and pedagogical competencies of future educators is based on a model for developing professional and pedagogical competence, which integrates the main foundations and factors of research work. The model is developed based on the organization of the process and the accuracy of the results.

The study of the effectiveness of the model educational process, divided into system and subsystem elements, ensures the achievement of gradual educational outcomes in a goal-oriented manner, as well as the ability to conduct and control the pedagogical process in a holistic and organized way.

The model includes the task of training and quality control mechanisms for future educators based on the requirements of the DTSS and social demand in preparing them for professional activities. Classroom instruction, qualification practice, independent learning processes, and the acquisition of work experience, along with the development of personal, professional, and individual qualities, ensure the formation of basic, universal, and special competencies of graduates.

The future educator should master a system of skills and qualifications related to professional activities, including: setting goals, selecting content, and organizing project work; synthesizing a range of problem-solving approaches or implementation strategies; carrying out tasks in a timely and creative manner; determining indicators that provide necessary information on the development of theoretical and practical knowledge, skills, and qualifications.

The methodological foundations for the development of professional and pedagogical competence were analyzed based on the stages and processes of organizing training in non-classroom and independent education. The content, forms, methods, and means of education in teaching preschool subjects were also analyzed. The future educator must also acquire the following competencies: setting goals, selecting content, and organizing project work; synthesizing possible solutions to problems or approaches to implementation; performing assigned tasks in a timely and creative manner; determining indicators that ensure access to information on the development of theoretical and practical knowledge, skills, and qualifications. In addition, the proposed model emphasizes the integration of theoretical training with practical experience through a systematic combination of classroom instruction, extracurricular activities, and independent learning. Special attention is given to reflective practice, self-assessment, and continuous professional development, enabling future educators to critically analyze their pedagogical activities and improve professional performance. The model also incorporates

feedback mechanisms from educational institutions and social stakeholders to ensure alignment with labor market requirements and contemporary preschool education standards. As a result, future educators develop the ability to apply innovative teaching methods, adapt to changing educational conditions, and effectively solve professional problems. This holistic approach ensures the sustainable development of professional and pedagogical competence and enhances the overall quality of educator training in higher education institutions.

Picture 1: Social order. Qualification requirements for preschool

Based on the competence-based approach, a model for improving the technological system of preparing future educators for professional activities was developed to increase the effectiveness of practical activities in acquiring knowledge, skills, and qualifications in the educational process. The model considers the influence of basic, general, and special competencies on the development of professional-pedagogical competence and the didactic development of professional competence structures.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the modernization of the higher education system in Uzbekistan requires a competency-based approach to the professional training of future preschool educators. The findings of this study demonstrate that the development of transversal-methodical competence plays a crucial role in fostering independent learning, critical thinking, and professional adaptability. The proposed training model, which is based on clear goal setting, systematic organization of educational content, and staged competence assessment, ensures the effective integration of innovative pedagogical technologies into the educational process. As a result, future educators are better prepared to respond to the demands of a rapidly changing educational environment. The implementation of this model contributes to improving the quality of preschool education and supports the successful professional development of graduates in accordance with modern educational standards.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 – PF-5847 on approval of the Concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030. <https://lex.uz/docs/-4545884>
2. Ergasheva, B. (2022). Talabalarining pedagogik modernizatsiya sharoitida kasbiy tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish. *Science and Innovation*, 1(B7), 401–405. (In Uzbek)
3. Barno, E. (2023). O'zbekistonda maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarining zamonaviy tizimi. *Research Focus International Scientific Journal*, 2(3), 103–105. (In Uzbek)
4. Ergasheva, B., Maxmudova, D., & Ramozonova, B. (2023). Technologies of preparing future teachers for professional activity on the basis of a competence-based approach. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 118–122. (In English)
5. Sadikova, Sh. A., & Ergasheva, B. Z. (2024, May 24). Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning ta'lim jarayonida transversal kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11288860> (In Uzbek)
6. Ergasheva, B. (2022). Improving the professional training of students in the conditions of pedagogical modernization. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7241508>
7. Ergasheva, B. Z. qizi. (2024). Technology of professional training of future teachers based on a competence-based approach. *Golden Brain*, 2(11), 101–105. <https://webgoldenbrain.com/index.php/gb/article/view/275> (In English)
8. Ergasheva, B. Z. (2025). Formation of transversal-methodological competence of future educators. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence*, 5(01), 451–453. <https://www.academicpublishers.org/journals/index.php/ijai/article/view/2386> (In English)
9. Sadikova, Sh. A., Yakubova, Z. Z., & Ergasheva, B. Z. (2025). Проектирование двуязычной образовательной и развивающей среды. *Научный журнал "Auezov University"*, (1). <https://doi.org/10.54251/2522-4026.2024.4.23au> (In Russian)
10. Ergasheva, B. Z. (2025). Development of transversal-methodical competence in future educators as a pedagogical problem. *Научный журнал "Auezov University"*, (1), 28–31. (In English)
11. Ergasheva, B. Z. qizi. (2025). Factors of the technology of development of transversal-methodical competence in future educators. <https://paresearchjournal.uz/index.php/journal/issue/view/13>, 1(18).

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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